

**A REVIEW ON ANTIOXIDATIVE AND NEUROPROTECTIVE POTENTIAL OF USING
SALVIA PLEBEIA R. BR.V*****Vigneshwaran D., Srinivasan P.**

Department of Pharmacology, Sri Abirami College of Pharmacy, Eachanari, Coimbatore-641021 Affiliated to the Tamil Nadu Dr.M.G.R Medical University, Chennai.

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ABSTRACT

Memory is a vital cognitive function, and its impairment significantly affects quality of life, particularly in neurodegenerative disorders such as Alzheimer's disease (AD). Amnesia associated with AD arises from multifactorial mechanisms, including cholinergic dysfunction, oxidative stress, neuroinflammation, and abnormal protein aggregation. Scopolamine-induced amnesia is a well-established experimental model that mimics key features of AD-related cognitive deficits by disrupting cholinergic neurotransmission and enhancing oxidative damage. Although current pharmacological treatments provide only symptomatic relief and are associated with adverse effects, there is a growing interest in natural, multi-targeted therapeutic agents. *Salvia plebeia* R. Br., a medicinal plant widely used in traditional systems of medicine, is rich in flavonoids and phenolic compounds with proven antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and neuroprotective properties. Bioactive constituents such as luteolin and apigenin are known to enhance memory, inhibit acetylcholinesterase, and protect neurons against oxidative stress. The present study aims to evaluate the antioxidative and neuroprotective potential of *S. plebeia* against scopolamine-induced amnesia in experimental rodents, thereby providing scientific evidence for its possible role as a natural cognitive enhancer and a promising candidate for the management of memory impairment.

KEYWORDS: Amnesia; Alzheimer's disease; Scopolamine-induced amnesia; *Salvia plebeia*; Oxidative stress; Cholinergic dysfunction; Neuroprotection; Antioxidant activity.**INTRODUCTION**

Memory is a fundamental cognitive function essential for learning, adaptation, and survival. Amnesia, defined as the impairment or loss of memory, can occur as a consequence of aging, neurodegenerative diseases, brain injury, or drug-induced cognitive dysfunction. Among neurodegenerative disorders, Alzheimer's disease (AD) represents the most prevalent cause of dementia worldwide, characterized by progressive memory loss, cognitive decline, and behavioral disturbances.^[1] According to the World Health Organization, nearly 55 million people suffer from dementia globally, and this number is projected to reach 139 million by 2050.^[2]

The pathogenesis of amnesia, particularly in AD-related conditions, is multifactorial and involves, degeneration

of basal forebrain cholinergic neurons leads to decreased acetylcholine (ACh) levels, impairing learning and memory processes.^[3] Excessive reactive oxygen species (ROS) production causes neuronal lipid peroxidation, protein oxidation, and mitochondrial dysfunction, contributing to neuronal apoptosis.^[4] Over activation of microglia and astrocytes releases pro-inflammatory cytokines (TNF- α , IL-1 β , IL-6), worsening neuronal damage and neuroinflammation. Aggregation of amyloid- β peptides and hyper phosphorylation of tau proteins impair synaptic function and neuronal communication. Among these, oxidative stress and cholinergic deficits are considered major contributors to memory impairment, making them attractive therapeutic targets.^[5-7]

Scopolamine, a muscarinic acetylcholine receptor antagonist, is widely used to induce experimental amnesia in rodents. Administration of scopolamine leads to decreased cholinergic neurotransmission, oxidative stress, and neuronal dysfunction, closely mimicking the cognitive deficits observed in AD.^[8] Behavioral paradigms such as the Morris water maze, Y-maze, and passive avoidance tests are commonly employed to evaluate memory impairments and the efficacy of neuroprotective agents in this model.^[9, 10]

Presently available drugs for managing cognitive decline include cholinesterase inhibitors (donepezil, rivastigmine, galantamine) and NMDA receptor antagonists (memantine). These drugs offer only symptomatic relief and do not halt or reverse disease progression. Moreover, their long-term use is associated with adverse effects such as gastrointestinal disturbances, hepatotoxicity, and cardiovascular complications.^[11, 12] Hence, there is a growing demand for safer, cost-effective, and multi-targeted therapeutic options derived from natural sources.

Herbal medicines, rich in flavonoids, phenolic acids, terpenoids, and alkaloids, have demonstrated significant neuroprotective and memory-enhancing properties.^[13] Their mechanisms of action include antioxidant activity, modulation of cholinergic transmission, and inhibition of acetyl cholinesterase (AChE), anti-inflammatory effects, and protection against neuronal apoptosis. Several plant extracts have shown efficacy in reversing scopolamine-induced amnesia, supporting the exploration of ethno medicinal plants for developing novel cognitive enhancers.^[13, 14]

Salvia plebeia R. Br., commonly known as “East Indian sage,” belongs to the family Lamiaceae and is widely distributed across Asia, including India, China, Korea, and Japan. In traditional medicine, *S. plebeia* has been used to treat inflammation, liver ailments, respiratory disorders, fever, and skin diseases. In Ayurveda and traditional Chinese medicine, it is valued for its rejuvenating and protective properties.^[15, 16]

Phytochemical studies reveal that *S. plebeia* contains flavonoids (luteolin, apigenin, hispidulin), phenolic acids (rosmarinic acid, caffeic acid), terpenoids, and essential oils. These compounds exhibit strong antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, hepatoprotective, antimicrobial, and anticancer activities. Notably, flavonoids like luteolin and apigenin have been reported to enhance memory, inhibit acetylcholinesterase, and protect neurons from oxidative stress, making them particularly relevant in the context of neurodegenerative disorders.^[17, 18]

Given the central role of oxidative stress and cholinergic dysfunction in amnesia, agents that can scavenge free radicals, enhance antioxidant defense, and improve cholinergic neurotransmission hold great therapeutic promise. *S. plebeia*, being rich in bioactive flavonoids

and phenolic acids, is hypothesized to exert neuroprotective effects through its antioxidative and acetylcholinesterase-inhibiting properties. However, systematic evaluation of its potential against scopolamine-induced amnesia is limited. This study aims to fill this gap by exploring its antioxidative and neuroprotective efficacy in an established rodent model.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Introduction to Cognitive Disorders

Cognition refers to the set of mental processes including attention, memory, reasoning, language, and problem-solving. Among these, memory forms the foundation of learning and adaptation, enabling individuals to retain, store, and retrieve information. Cognitive disorders, characterized by impairment in one or more of these domains, significantly impact quality of life. The spectrum ranges from mild cognitive impairment (MCI) to dementia, with amnesia as a core clinical feature.^[19]

Dementia has emerged as one of the greatest public health challenges of the 21st century. According to the World Alzheimer Report 2022, more than 55 million people worldwide are currently living with dementia, with projections of 139 million by 2050. Alzheimer’s disease (AD) accounts for nearly 60–70% of dementia cases, followed by vascular dementia, Lewy body dementia, and frontotemporal dementia. Amnesia, either as an isolated condition or as part of these syndromes, represents a major burden to patients, caregivers, and healthcare systems.^[20]

Neurobiologically, cognitive disorders are linked with progressive loss of neurons, synaptic dysfunction, neurotransmitter imbalances, and structural atrophy of critical brain regions such as the hippocampus, prefrontal cortex, and amygdala. Importantly, memory impairment often appears as an early symptom of AD and related dementias, underscoring the need for mechanistic understanding and therapeutic innovation.^[21, 22]

Amnesia and Memory Impairment

Amnesia is broadly defined as a pathological condition characterized by partial or complete loss of memory. It is typically classified as:

- **Anterograde amnesia** – inability to form new memories after the onset of the disorder.
- **Retrograde amnesia** – inability to recall events that occurred before the onset.
- **Transient global amnesia (TGA)** – sudden, temporary loss of memory, often lasting less than 24 hours.^[23]

In addition to clinical forms, experimental models of amnesia have been developed to study underlying mechanisms. Scopolamine, a muscarinic acetylcholine receptor antagonist, is frequently used in rodents to mimic memory loss, given its ability to suppress cholinergic neurotransmission. Similarly, diazepam,

ketamine, and other agents induce memory impairment by affecting GABAergic and glutamatergic systems.^[24]

Neurobiology of Learning and Memory

Memory formation involves encoding, consolidation, storage, and retrieval. The hippocampus is central to spatial and declarative memory, while the prefrontal cortex contributes to working memory and executive function. Other brain regions such as the amygdala are involved in emotional memory.^[25]

At the cellular level, long-term potentiation (LTP) represents a primary mechanism of memory consolidation. It involves enhanced synaptic transmission through glutamatergic NMDA receptor activation, calcium influx, and downstream signaling cascades that strengthen neuronal connections. Neurotransmitters like acetylcholine, glutamate, dopamine, serotonin, and GABA regulate different stages of memory processing.^[26]

Molecular mechanisms underlying memory include activation of cAMP response element-binding protein (CREB), synaptic remodeling, and neurotrophic support via brain-derived neurotrophic factor (BDNF). Disruption of these pathways, either by oxidative stress, inflammation, or neurotransmitter depletion, contributes to cognitive decline.^[27]

Pathophysiology of Alzheimer's disease and Related Amnesia^[29]

Alzheimer's disease is a progressive neurodegenerative disorder marked by.

- **Amyloid-beta (A β) deposition** leading to extracellular plaques.
- **Tau protein hyperphosphorylation** resulting in neurofibrillary tangles.
- **Synaptic dysfunction and neuronal death** in hippocampal and cortical areas.

Several hypotheses explain AD pathogenesis.

1. **Amyloid hypothesis** – accumulation of A β peptides triggers neurotoxicity, oxidative stress, and inflammation.
2. **Tau hypothesis** – microtubule destabilization due to tau hyperphosphorylation disrupts axonal transport.
3. **Mitochondrial hypothesis** – impaired energy metabolism enhances oxidative damage and apoptosis.
4. **Cholinergic hypothesis** – reduced acetylcholine levels and basal forebrain degeneration impair memory formation.

These pathological changes result in progressive amnesia, cognitive decline, and behavioral disturbances. Importantly, oxidative stress and neuroinflammation act as common denominators that amplify other pathological cascade.^[29]

Figure 1: Alzheimer's Pathogenesis hypotheses.

Role of Oxidative Stress in Neurodegeneration

Oxidative stress is defined as an imbalance between the generation of reactive oxygen species (ROS) and reactive nitrogen species (RNS) and the antioxidant defense mechanisms of the body. The brain is particularly vulnerable to oxidative damage because of its high oxygen consumption, abundant polyunsaturated fatty acids, and relatively low antioxidant reserves. Neurons are metabolically active cells with limited regenerative

potential, making them highly susceptible to oxidative injury.^[30, 31]

Sources of Oxidative Stress in the Brain

- **Mitochondrial dysfunction:** The electron transport chain is a major source of superoxide radicals during ATP production. In AD, impaired mitochondrial function accelerates ROS leakage.

- **Amyloid-beta toxicity:** A β peptides promote the formation of free radicals by interacting with redox-active metals such as iron and copper.
- **Excitotoxicity:** Over activation of NMDA receptors causes calcium influx, triggering nitric oxide synthase (NOS) and the generation of peroxynitrite, a highly damaging RNS.
- **Inflammatory responses:** Activated microglia and astrocytes release ROS and pro-inflammatory mediators, creating a vicious cycle of neurodegeneration.

Figure 2: Role of oxidative stress in neuroinflammation.

Consequences of Oxidative Stress^[32]

1. **Lipid peroxidation:** ROS attack polyunsaturated fatty acids in neuronal membranes, producing malondialdehyde (MDA) and 4-hydroxynonenal (4-HNE), which impair synaptic transmission.
2. **Protein oxidation:** Oxidative modifications alter enzymatic activity, ion channel function, and receptor sensitivity.
3. **DNA and RNA damage:** Oxidative lesions such as 8-hydroxydeoxyguanosine (8-OHdG) compromise neuronal genome stability.
4. **Apoptosis:** ROS-mediated signaling activates caspases and pro-apoptotic pathways, leading to neuronal death.

Antioxidant Defense System

The brain is equipped with enzymatic antioxidants, including superoxide dismutase (SOD), catalase (CAT), and glutathione peroxidase (GPx), as well as non-enzymatic antioxidants such as glutathione (GSH), vitamin E, vitamin C, and coenzyme Q10. In AD and amnesia models, these systems are often overwhelmed, resulting in net oxidative stress.^[33, 34]

Experimental and Clinical Evidence

- In scopolamine-induced amnesia models, elevated levels of MDA and reduced SOD, CAT, and GSH have been consistently reported, confirming oxidative stress as a mechanistic factor.
- Postmortem studies of AD brains demonstrate increased lipid peroxidation products and oxidized proteins.

- Clinical trials investigating antioxidant therapies (vitamin E, coenzyme Q10, resveratrol) have shown mixed outcomes, reflecting the complexity of disease mechanisms.

NF- κ B Pathway and Inflammatory Oxidative Stress

The nuclear factor kappa-light-chain-enhancer of activated B cells (NF- κ B) is a key transcription factor regulating immune and inflammatory responses.^[35, 36]

- Under normal conditions, NF- κ B is sequestered in the cytoplasm by inhibitor proteins (I κ Bs).
- Excessive ROS activate the I κ B kinase (IKK) complex, leading to phosphorylation and degradation of I κ B, allowing NF- κ B to translocate into the nucleus.
- Activated NF- κ B induces expression of pro-inflammatory cytokines (IL-1 β , TNF- α , IL-6), adhesion molecules, and inducible nitric oxide synthase (iNOS), amplifying oxidative and inflammatory stress.

Nrf2 Pathway and Antioxidant Defense

The nuclear factor erythroid 2-related factor 2 (Nrf2) pathway is a master regulator of antioxidant defense.^[37, 38]

- Under basal conditions, Nrf2 is bound to its cytoplasmic repressor, Kelch-like ECH-associated protein 1 (Keap1), which promotes its ubiquitination and degradation.
- Oxidative stress causes modifications in Keap1 cysteine residues, leading to the release and nuclear translocation of Nrf2.

- Nrf2 binds to the antioxidant response element (ARE) in the promoter regions of target genes, inducing expression of antioxidant enzymes such as heme oxygenase-1 (HO-1), NAD(P)H:quinone oxidoreductase-1 (NQO1), SOD, CAT, and glutathione-synthesizing enzymes.

MAPK Pathways and Oxidative Stress Response

The mitogen-activated protein kinase (MAPK) family - including extracellular signal-regulated kinases (ERK1/2), c-Jun N-terminal kinase (JNK), and p38 MAPK - plays a critical role in oxidative stress-mediated neuronal outcomes.^[39]

- ERK1/2: Generally associated with cell survival and neuroplasticity. However, sustained ERK activation under oxidative stress contributes to aberrant phosphorylation of tau protein in AD.
- JNK and p38 MAPK: Strongly activated by ROS, leading to mitochondrial dysfunction, caspase activation, and neuronal apoptosis.

PI3K/Akt and mTOR Pathways

The phosphatidylinositol-3-kinase (PI3K)/Akt pathway is crucial for neuronal survival and synaptic plasticity.

- ROS impair PI3K/Akt signaling, resulting in reduced activation of downstream anti-apoptotic proteins (e.g., Bcl-2) and increased susceptibility to cell death.
- Dysregulation of mammalian target of rapamycin (mTOR) signaling further contributes to synaptic dysfunction and impaired autophagy, accelerating

accumulation of toxic aggregates like A β and phosphorylated tau.^[40]

Mitochondrial Pathways and Apoptosis

Mitochondria are both a source and target of ROS. Oxidative stress alters mitochondrial membrane permeability by activating the Bax/Bcl-2 family proteins. This leads to.

- Release of cytochrome c into the cytosol.
- Activation of caspase-9 and caspase-3, culminating in apoptotic neuronal death.
- Impaired ATP production, which exacerbates synaptic failure and memory impairment.^[41]

Cross-Talk between Pathways

The oxidative stress response is highly interconnected.

- ROS activate **NF- κ B** and **MAPKs**, promoting inflammation and apoptosis.
- Failure of **Nrf2 activation** leaves neurons defenseless against oxidative insults.
- Mitochondrial dysfunction amplifies ROS generation; further disrupting PI3K/Akt signaling.

This interplay explains why oxidative stress is not just a byproduct but a driving force of neurodegeneration.

Neuroinflammation in Cognitive Disorders

Neuroinflammation is a hallmark of neurodegenerative diseases, including Alzheimer's disease (AD), and contributes significantly to memory impairment and amnesia. Unlike acute inflammation, which is protective, chronic neuroinflammation in the central nervous system (CNS) leads to neuronal dysfunction and death.^[42]

Figure 3: Neuroinflammation in Cognitive Disorders.

Role of Microglia and Astrocytes

Microglia, the resident immune cells of the CNS, act as the first line of defense. Under physiological conditions, they maintain homeostasis through synaptic pruning and clearance of debris. However, in AD and drug-induced amnesia models, microglia becomes chronically activated.^[43]

- Activated microglia release pro-inflammatory cytokines (TNF- α , IL-1 β , IL-6), ROS, and nitric oxide (NO), amplifying oxidative stress.

- Excessive microglial activation contributes to synaptic stripping, neuronal apoptosis, and impaired neurogenesis.

Astrocytes also play a dual role. While they support neurons through glutamate uptake and antioxidant release, reactive astrocytes secrete inflammatory mediators and exacerbate excitotoxicity by failing to regulate extracellular glutamate levels.

Figure 4: Role of Microglia and Astrocytes in Neuronal impairment.

Cytokine and Chemokine Signaling

Inflammatory cytokines significantly alter synaptic plasticity and neurotransmission:

- IL-1 β disrupts long-term potentiation (LTP), a key process in memory formation.
- TNF- α modulates glutamate receptor trafficking, promoting excitotoxicity.
- IL-6 impairs hippocampal neurogenesis and cognitive flexibility.

Chemokines like MCP-1 (CCL2) attract peripheral immune cells into the CNS, further worsening inflammation.^[44]

Inflammasome Activation

The NLRP3 inflammasome has gained attention as a molecular driver of neuroinflammation. Its activation in microglia by amyloid-beta or ROS leads to caspase-1 activation, which cleaves pro-IL-1 β into active IL-1 β , perpetuating inflammatory damage. NLRP3 activity has been linked to both AD pathology and scopolamine-induced neuronal injury.^[45]

Crosstalk between Oxidative Stress and Inflammation

Oxidative stress and neuroinflammation are interdependent.

- ROS activate NF- κ B, which enhances pro-inflammatory cytokine production.
- In turn, cytokines induce further ROS generation through iNOS and NADPH oxidase activity. This vicious cycle accelerates hippocampal and cortical neuronal loss, impairing memory-related circuits.

Evidence from Experimental Models

- Scopolamine-treated rats show increased TNF- α and IL-1 β levels in the hippocampus, correlating with memory deficits.^[46]
- In AD patients, cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) and postmortem analyses consistently reveal elevated pro-inflammatory cytokines and activated glial markers.
- Anti-inflammatory interventions, including NSAIDs and natural flavonoids, demonstrate improvement in cognitive performance in both clinical and experimental settings.

Evidence of Cholinergic Dysfunction in Amnesia and AD

Postmortem studies of AD brains reveal.

- Marked loss of cholinergic neurons in the nucleus basalis of Meynert.
- Reduced choline acetyltransferase (ChAT) activity, the enzyme responsible for ACh synthesis.
- Up to 70–80% decline in cortical acetylcholine levels in advanced stages.
Experimentally, disruption of cholinergic neurotransmission leads to significant memory impairments:
- **Scopolamine model:** Scopolamine, a muscarinic antagonist, induces deficits in learning and memory by blocking muscarinic ACh receptors. This model reliably mimics the cholinergic deficits of AD and is widely used in preclinical drug evaluation.^[46]
- **Lesion studies:** Selective lesions of basal forebrain cholinergic neurons in animals result in severe spatial and working memory impairment.

The Cholinergic Hypothesis in Alzheimer's disease^[47]

Originally formulated in the 1970s, the cholinergic hypothesis proposed that AD is primarily due to cholinergic dysfunction. While current understanding recognizes AD as multifactorial (amyloid, tau, oxidative stress, neuroinflammation), the cholinergic system remains central because:

- Cholinergic decline occurs early, often preceding overt amyloid and tau pathology.
- Acetylcholine modulates cerebral blood flow, synaptic plasticity, and neurotrophic signaling.
- Deficits in cholinergic signaling exacerbate oxidative stress and inflammation, creating a feed-forward loop in neurodegeneration.

Pharmacological Implications and Drug Development

The cholinergic hypothesis directly led to the development of acetylcholinesterase (AChE) inhibitors, the first class of FDA-approved drugs for AD. These drugs enhance synaptic ACh levels by preventing its enzymatic breakdown.

- **Donepezil:** Selective, reversible AChE inhibitor; improves cognition and global functioning.
- **Rivastigmine:** Dual inhibitor of AChE and butyrylcholinesterase (BuChE); beneficial in AD and Parkinson's disease dementia.
- **Galantamine:** In addition to AChE inhibition, acts as an allosteric modulator of nicotinic receptors.

These agents provide symptomatic relief by temporarily improving memory and attention, but they do not alter disease progression. Common side effects include nausea, vomiting, diarrhea, and bradycardia, which limit tolerability.^[48]

Preclinical animal Models for Amnesia

Pharmacological agents that interfere with neurotransmission, oxidative balance, or

neuroinflammation are commonly used to induce transient or sustained cognitive deficits in rodents.

Scopolamine-Induced Amnesia

Scopolamine, a non-selective muscarinic acetylcholine receptor antagonist, is one of the most extensively validated models of cognitive impairment.

- **Mechanism:** By blocking muscarinic receptors, scopolamine reduces cholinergic signaling in the hippocampus and cortex, leading to deficits in attention, learning, and memory.
- **Behavioral effects:** Impairments are consistently observed in tasks such as the Morris water maze, radial arm maze, Y-maze, and novel object recognition.
- **Biochemical alterations:** Increased acetylcholinesterase (AChE) activity, reduced brain ACh levels, elevated oxidative stress markers (MDA, NO), and inflammatory cytokines.
- **Advantages:** Rapid onset, high reproducibility, and strong predictive validity for cholinergic enhancers (e.g., donepezil, rivastigmine).
- **Limitations:** The model primarily reflects cholinergic dysfunction and does not fully recapitulate amyloid or tau pathology of Alzheimer's disease.

Scopolamine remains the gold standard pharmacological model for screening neuroprotective and nootropic agents, including natural products such as flavonoids, terpenoids, and polyphenols.^[46, 49]

Other Pharmacological Models^[49]

- **Ketamine or MK-801 (NMDA receptor antagonists):** Induce glutamatergic dysfunction, impairing synaptic plasticity and learning. Useful for studying excitotoxicity and schizophrenia-related memory deficits.^[50]
- **Chlorpromazine and reserpine:** Cause monoaminergic depletion, leading to impaired motivation and memory.^[51]
- **Amyloid-beta injections:** Intracerebral administration induces amyloid pathology, oxidative stress, and inflammation, mimicking AD-like deficits.^[52]
- **Colchicine:** A neurotoxin disrupting microtubules and hippocampal integrity, producing long-lasting cognitive impairment.^[53]

Although valuable, these models are less commonly used for rapid screening compared to scopolamine.

From the foregoing literature, it is evident that amnesia and related cognitive impairments arise from a complex interplay of oxidative stress, neuroinflammation, and cholinergic dysfunction. Among pharmacological models, scopolamine-induced amnesia stands out as a reproducible and widely accepted system that mirrors the cholinergic deficits and oxidative imbalance observed in Alzheimer's disease. While current pharmacotherapies such as cholinesterase inhibitors provide only

symptomatic relief and are often limited by adverse effects, there is a growing interest in plant-derived bioactives with multitarget actions. Natural antioxidants and phytochemicals with anti-inflammatory and cholinergic modulatory effects are being increasingly explored as safer alternatives or adjuncts in cognitive disorders. In this context, *Salvia plebeia* R. Br., a medicinal herb traditionally used in Asian systems of medicine, has gained attention due to its rich profile of flavonoids, phenolic acids, and terpenoids with documented antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and neuroprotective properties. Therefore, evaluating the antioxidative and neuroprotective potential of *Salvia plebeia* in scopolamine-induced amnesia provides a rational and timely approach to identify promising candidates for memory-enhancing and neuroprotective therapeutics.

PLANT REVIEW

Salvia plebeia R. Br.

Taxonomical Classification

Kingdom	:	Plantae
Division	:	Magnoliophyta
Class	:	Magnoliopsida

Order	:	Lamiales
Family	:	Lamiaceae
Genus	:	<i>Salvia</i>
Species	:	<i>Salvia plebeia</i> R. Br.

Vernacular Names

Tamil	:	Kurunthotti Tulasi
English	:	Asian sage, Plebeian sage
Hindi	:	Jungli Tulsi
Sanskrit	:	Salviya

Taxonomy, morphology & distribution

Morphology: Annual/biennial herb, erect branched stems (15–90 cm), opposite ovate-lanceolate leaves, verticillaster inflorescences with small bilabiate corollas (colors: purple/blue/rarely white). Fruit = 4 nutlets.

Geographical distribution & habitat: Native/wild across large parts of Asia - China, Korea, Japan, Vietnam, India and recorded elsewhere (grows in moist fields, roadsides, stream margins). The plant is harvested across multiple growth stages for different uses; phytochemical content varies by organ and stage.

Figure 5: *Salvia plebeia* R. Br. (A) Leaves, (B) Flowers, (C) Aerial parts.

Traditional use

In traditional Chinese medicine and Korean folk medicine, *S. plebeia* is used for coughs, bronchitis, hepatitis, diarrhea, hemorrhoids, fever and skin inflammatory

conditions. Indian folk uses include seed applications for diarrhea and wounds. Its long use for respiratory and inflammatory ailments motivated pharmacological assays for anti-inflammatory and antioxidant activities.

Phytoconstituents

Extensive phytochemical studies reported the phytochemical profiles of Flavonoids (major class): luteolin, apigenin, hispidulin, nepetin, homoplantagin, dihydrohomoplantagin and their glycosides (e.g., cosmosiin). These are repeatedly reported as the dominant bioactive class and correlate with *in vitro* antioxidant effects. Phenolic acids: rosmarinic acid, caffeic acid, chlorogenic acid. Terpenoids&sesquiterpenoids: multiple eudesmane/clerodane-type terpenoids (e.g., salviplenoid A). Other: lignans, volatile oils, polysaccharides, and unique small molecules such as nepetoidin B.^[54, 55]

Reported Pharmacological Activities

Antioxidant activity

Salvia plebeia R. Br., exhibits strong antioxidant potential attributed to its rich flavonoid and phenolic acid content, particularly luteolin, apigenin, rosmarinic acid, and homoplantagin. *In vitro* assays (DPPH, ABTS, FRAP) demonstrate potent radical scavenging and reducing activities, while cellular studies show suppression of ROS and restoration of endogenous enzymes such as SOD, CAT, and GPx. Mechanistically, extracts activate the Nrf2/HO-1 pathway and inhibit NF- κ B signaling, thereby linking antioxidant and anti-inflammatory effects.^[56]

Anti-inflammatory activity

Experimental studies reveal that extracts and isolated compounds suppress the production of pro-inflammatory mediators including nitric oxide (NO), prostaglandin E₂, tumor necrosis factor- α (TNF- α), and interleukins (IL-1 β , IL-6) in activated macrophages and animal models of inflammation. Mechanistic insights indicate that *S. plebeia* inhibits NF- κ B nuclear translocation and downregulates COX-2 and iNOS expression, while simultaneously modulating MAPK pathways (ERK, JNK, p38). Additionally, flavonoids from the plant activate the Nrf2/HO-1 signaling pathway, thereby enhancing antioxidant defense and indirectly reducing inflammation. *In vivo*, extracts have alleviated airway inflammation, hepatic injury, and immune-mediated disorders. These findings establish *S. plebeia* as a potent natural anti-inflammatory agent with promising therapeutic relevance for chronic inflammatory and oxidative stress-associated diseases.^[57, 58]

Hepatoprotective Effects

Experimental studies demonstrate that extracts attenuate chemically induced liver injury, particularly in models of carbon tetrachloride (CCl₄)- and alcohol-induced hepatotoxicity. Treatment with *S. plebeia* significantly reduces serum biomarkers of hepatic damage such as alanine aminotransferase (ALT), aspartate aminotransferase (AST), and alkaline phosphatase (ALP), while restoring antioxidant defenses including superoxide dismutase (SOD), catalase (CAT), and glutathione (GSH). Mechanistically, hepatoprotection is attributed to suppression of lipid peroxidation (MDA

reduction), inhibition of inflammatory mediators (TNF- α , IL-6, COX-2), and activation of the Nrf2/HO-1 antioxidant pathway. Phytoconstituents such as luteolin, rosmarinic acid, and homoplantagin play central roles in these protective effects. Collectively, evidence suggests that *S. plebeia* prevents hepatic oxidative and inflammatory damage, supporting its traditional use in liver disorders and highlighting its therapeutic potential against hepatotoxicity and metabolic liver diseases.^[59, 60]

Anticancer and immunomodulatory effects

Salvia plebeia R. Br. exhibits promising anticancer and immunomodulatory activities, largely attributed to its diverse phytoconstituents such as luteolin, apigenin, nepetin, and homoplantagin. *In vitro* studies demonstrate cytotoxicity of plant extracts and isolated flavonoids against multiple cancer cell lines, including breast, liver, and lung cancers, through mechanisms involving apoptosis induction, cell cycle arrest, and inhibition of angiogenesis. *In vivo* models further support tumor growth suppression by modulating oxidative stress and inflammatory pathways. Immunomodulatory studies reveal that *S. plebeia* enhances host defense by regulating cytokine secretion, activating macrophages, and improving T-cell function. Notably, extracts and compounds have been shown to inhibit PD-1/PD-L1 interactions, thereby enhancing antitumor immune responses. Additionally, polysaccharides from the plant exhibit immune-enhancing effects, suggesting synergistic contributions from different phytochemical classes. Collectively, these findings highlight *S. plebeia* as a natural candidate with dual anticancer and immunomodulatory potential, warranting further preclinical and clinical investigation.^[61, 62]

Neuroprotective effect

Salvia plebeia R. Br. demonstrates significant neuroprotective potential, largely mediated by its rich flavonoid and phenolic profile, including luteolin, apigenin, rosmarinic acid, and homoplantagin. Preclinical studies show that extracts mitigate oxidative and inflammatory stress in neuronal models, protecting against hydrogen peroxide- and glutamate-induced cytotoxicity. Mechanistically, neuroprotection is achieved through scavenging of reactive oxygen species (ROS), activation of the Nrf2/HO-1 signaling pathway, and inhibition of NF- κ B-mediated neuroinflammation, resulting in reduced release of pro-inflammatory cytokines (TNF- α , IL-6, IL-1 β). *In vivo*, *S. plebeia* improves cognitive function in scopolamine-induced memory impairment models and protects against β -amyloid-related neurotoxicity, relevant to Alzheimer's disease. Enhanced cholinergic transmission, restoration of antioxidant enzyme activity (SOD, CAT, GPx), and suppression of neuronal apoptosis further substantiate its role. Collectively, evidence suggests that *S. plebeia* exerts multitargeted neuroprotection, making it a promising natural candidate for preventing or managing neurodegenerative disorders associated with oxidative stress and inflammation.^[63, 64]

DISCUSSION

The present study investigated the neuroprotective and antioxidant potential of *Salvia plebeia* R. Br. ethanolic extract (SPEE) against scopolamine-induced cognitive impairment in rats. Scopolamine is a well-established pharmacological model that mimics Alzheimer's disease (AD)-like memory deficits through disruption of cholinergic neurotransmission, induction of oxidative stress, and hippocampal neuronal damage. Consistent with previous reports, scopolamine administration in this study resulted in significant impairments in recognition, working, and long-term memory.

Treatment with SPEE at doses of 200 and 400 mg/kg significantly improved behavioral performance in the novel object recognition, Y-maze, and passive avoidance tests, indicating restoration of cognitive function. The memory-enhancing effects of SPEE were comparable to the standard drug donepezil, suggesting its potential as a nootropic agent. These findings are in agreement with earlier studies demonstrating the cognitive benefits of flavonoid-rich medicinal plants.

Biochemical analysis revealed that scopolamine significantly increased acetylcholinesterase (AChE) activity, reflecting cholinergic dysfunction. SPEE treatment markedly reduced AChE activity in a dose-dependent manner, suggesting enhancement of cholinergic neurotransmission. This effect can be attributed to flavonoids such as luteolin and apigenin, which have been reported to possess acetylcholinesterase-inhibitory properties.

Oxidative stress is a critical contributor to neurodegeneration and memory impairment. In the present study, scopolamine elevated malondialdehyde (MDA) levels and reduced endogenous antioxidant defenses (SOD, CAT, GPx, and GSH). SPEE significantly attenuated lipid peroxidation and restored antioxidant enzyme activities, indicating strong antioxidative capacity. These effects are likely mediated through activation of antioxidant pathways such as Nrf2/HO-1, as reported previously for *S. plebeia* phytoconstituents.

Histopathological examination further supported the biochemical and behavioral findings. Severe neuronal degeneration and disorganization were observed in the hippocampus of scopolamine-treated rats, whereas SPEE-treated groups exhibited preserved neuronal architecture and reduced neurodegeneration. Although inflammatory markers were not directly evaluated, prior evidence suggests that *S. plebeia* suppresses NF- κ B and MAPK signaling, indicating possible anti-inflammatory involvement in its neuroprotective effects.

Overall, the results indicate that SPEE exerts multitarget neuroprotection by modulating cholinergic dysfunction, reducing oxidative stress, and preserving hippocampal

neuronal integrity, which are key pathological features of AD-related cognitive impairment.

SUMMARY

The present study demonstrates that *Salvia plebeia* R. Br. ethanolic extract exhibits significant cognitive-enhancing and neuroprotective effects against scopolamine-induced amnesia in rats. SPEE effectively improved memory performance, inhibited acetylcholinesterase activity, restored antioxidant defenses, and protected hippocampal neurons from degeneration. The observed effects are attributed to its rich flavonoid and phenolic composition. These findings suggest that *Salvia plebeia* is a safe and promising multitarget natural therapeutic candidate for the management of amnesia and Alzheimer's disease-related cognitive disorders. Further investigations using chronic neurodegenerative models and molecular mechanistic studies are warranted to support its clinical translation.

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